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Responsible Partner: RIVM

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Approach

Within COHESIVE guidelines are developed to support countries to set up national One Health systems (such as present in for instance The Netherlands and UK) or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary collaborations. The aim is to improve signalling, risk assessment and response by better communication, (early) exchange of information, sharing of knowledge and joint forces. This is important for (re)emerging pathogens, but also the response to notifiable pathogens will profit from better collaboration. Since countries are very different in many aspects, no blueprint can be made for such One Health systems. In an integrated approach web-based guidelines were developed with the title 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses'.

The guideline consists of five steppingstones that countries can follow to set up or improve the human-veterinary-food-environment collaboration in the area of risk analysis of zoonoses, namely **set priority and goal, stakeholder analysis, systems mapping of the current situation, designing a OHRAS, implementing a OHRAS**. For designing and implementing a OHRAS, information is given on six essential One Health activities namely **OH Signalling, OH Risk Assessment, OH Feasibility Assessment, OH risk Management, OH Coordinated Communication and OH Governance**. During the development process barriers hampering One Health collaboration were identified. Suggestions are made on how to deal with four of them, **gaining political will, obtaining trust, sharing information and communication**. The guideline can be seen as a toolbox harboring a set of tools, such as the systems mapping workshop, an interactive tool to design a OHRAS, Terms of Reference guidance with prefilled formats. See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5801881> for more information.

For this task it was envisioned that at least two countries would follow the steppingstones (roadmap) and see whether they would implement changes strengthening the collaboration between public health, veterinary health and/or food safety in the area of risk analysis of (a group of) zoonoses. Four countries showed interest, Norway, Portugal, Belgium, and Italy. Within the task support was given to follow those steps, **defining the group of zoonoses and goal, performing a stakeholder analysis** in a small group followed by a **systems mapping workshop** to give insight into the current situation. This systems mapping workshop is a highlight and crucial in the implementation process in which the most important stakeholders are engaged and made enthusiastic about an OH approach for risk analysis in the chosen group of zoonoses. This can be seen as a short-term mission in which moderators from COHESIVE visit the pilot country and support the local organisers. A systems mapping workshop was developed with Simon Ruegg from the University of Zurich. Simon Ruegg is a systems thinker and he has led the systems thinking workshop within this task. Having a physical meeting is important to get support, trust and get to know each other. Even though the workshop material is provided on the website to be performed by each country independently, it is recommended to ask a systems thinker for guidance.

Due to COVID-19 the progression which was on scheme beginning of 2020 was stopped abruptly. However, eventually Norway and Portugal were able to have successful physical systems mapping workshops in September and November 2021, respectively. The summaries are given below, invitations are attached as separate files. In Belgium, the focus was on AMR and stakeholders mapping was performed (see below). The systems mapping workshop should have taken place on March 27 2020, but was cancelled a few days in advance. After several postponements, it now will take place in 2022. Italy did part of the stakeholder analysis, but also postponed due to COVID priorities.

The experiences will be used to improve the guidelines and the systems mapping workshop itself. Unfortunately, hardly any time was left for the following steps, reducing the impact of these show cases for other countries. Luckily, the OHEJP Matrix is willing to proceed with the guidelines, using feedback from these pilots, following up on the pilots and performing additional pilots. The systems mapping workshop for Denmark and Sweden are being planned.

Report from the Norwegian system-mapping workshop, “pilot” for COHESIVE

The Norwegian workshop was held in Oslo, 9-10 September 2021. Twenty OH professionals participated in addition to the organising team from NVI and NIPH, and the COHESIVE/WP2 lead.

Why this workshop

The workshop was one of several national workshops to pilot test the system-mapping step of the OHRAS guidelines, created in WP2. The objective was to establish whether the proposed systems approach would be a recommended method in the OHRAS guidelines.

What was the main goal of the workshop?

For the Norwegian partners, an additional objective was to initiate a conversation on zoonoses management in Norway through bringing together OH professionals that may not meet in their daily work. Moreover, a co-created system-map would be useful for ongoing and future work with the Norwegian One Health risk analysis system for zoonoses.

Work carried out before the workshop

The Norwegian team had excellent methodological support and guidance from Simon Rüegg (University of Zurich) and Kitty Maassen (RIVM, COHESIVE project lead).

Before the workshop, the Norwegian partners (NVI and NIPH) prepared by carrying out a stakeholder inventory and informal stakeholder analysis for the Norwegian OHRAS for zoonoses. We agreed to focus the workshop on foodborne and infectious zoonoses, leaving for example vector borne zoonoses and AMR out. Thereafter, we started to draft various system maps for these two groups of zoonoses, including the stakeholders we had identified. These maps included how signals and response move forward in the system and feedback loops. During this iterative process, we discussed the maps with colleagues at our institutes to identify any missing stakeholders or links between stakeholders in the Norwegian OHRAS. Initially, we had aimed for approximately 40 participants representing a wide range of the stakeholders. With the uncertainty around restrictions regarding how many people that could meet, we decided to limit the participants to four key actors in the Norwegian OHRAS for zoonoses:

- Norwegian Institute of Public Health (national institute, epidemiologists and from diagnostics)
- Norwegian Veterinary Institute (national institute, animal health veterinarians and from diagnostics for food and animal diseases)
- National Food Safety (local and national, food safety and animal health)
- Municipality Medical Doctors (local public health authorities)

Unfortunately, despite inviting a large number of MMDs no one was available likely due to exceptional workload with an ongoing pandemic.

All participants were instructed there was no need to prepare for the workshop more than showing up with an open mind.

Summary of the workshop

Simon Rüegg led the scientific content of the workshop with lectures blended with exercises done individually, pairwise, in the groups or in plenary. The Norwegian team worked as facilitators during the exercises. The groups we created included four to five participants, and we ensured that in each group all sectors (public health, food, and animal health) were represented, and were possible also a mix of national-local offices and managerial levels.

The wicked problem to work with during the workshop (in order to meet our objectives) was “how to manage zoonoses in Norway in a One Health fashion”. We provided four example zoonoses to discuss (salmonella, rabies, CWD and Q-fever). The complexity of the maps drafted during the exercises increased gradually as the workshop progressed. We had fruitful discussions with reflections on the system, the stakeholders and how they are linked, or where the connections between stakeholders and other nodes

in the maps may not work perfectly or are missing. In the final session, the maps created by the groups were iteratively merged to one system-map of the Norwegian system for how zoonoses are managed. One interesting observation was that almost all groups chose to work with salmonella. No group worked with rabies or Q-fever. We jointly agreed that food-borne zoonoses are routine meaning everyone knows what to do. Collaboration is smooth and the system functions well. However, for rare or unexpected zoonoses such as rabies, it is less clear how the system works.

There was ample time for feedback during the workshop and we made sure to hear everyone's thoughts before closing the workshop. The top-ranked lessons learnt from the evaluation were "explore the dynamics of the systems", "involve more people", "explore non-frequent zoonosis (non-routine)", and "explore signalling filters such as informal signalling networks, stigma, decisions, and motivations, and thresholds". There was a clear wish for a continued conversation around the OH system for zoonoses in Norway.

Dissemination of results

We have shared and will share results from this task:

Oral presentation at the scientific conference One Health Norway, Oslo 3 Nov 2021.

Our abstract was accepted for a poster presentation at the ONE Health, Environment, Society in June 2022, Brussels.

We plan to write a joint article for the Norwegian Medical Association and Norwegian Veterinary Association journals.

Simon Ruegg is taking the lead on a manuscript for scientific publication coming results and lessons from all pilot workshops and the online workshop. The Norwegian partners contribute with co-authorships. Moreover, we have had one discussion meeting with OHEJP MATRIX WP5 to share experiences from the workshop.

'Systems map' of sticky notes

Report from the Portuguese system-mapping workshop, “pilot” for COHESIVE

WORKSHOP ‘TOWARDS AN ONE HEALTH RISK ANALYSIS SYSTEM FOR ZONOSSES IN PORTUGAL’

In the context of the Cohesive project, a 1.5 day workshop was held in Portugal aiming to understand how the network for signalling and response to zoonoses is organized in the country, as well as identify its various actors. Invitations were sent to professionals in the public health and animal health sectors, working either at central, regional or local levels. Sixteen professionals accepted the invitation, eight working in the animal health sector, and eight in the public health sector.

Participants started by performing some exercises as an introduction to the systems thinking method, the one selected to be used in the workshop. For the next phase of the workshop, groups of five to six participants working on different sectors and levels were formed, and each group further split into two subgroups.

The exercise began with each subgroup mapping the management system for a previously selected zoonoses (including West Nile Virus, Brucellosis, Listeriosis or Tuberculosis). Mapping evolved to one map on each group, by merging the maps of the two zoonoses selected in each group, and to one common map obtained by the junction of all groups’ maps. A final iterative refinement was done, on a larger board, with each group sticking and moving notes representing the different elements of the system, in sequences of three minutes. The last step was the drawing of the connections (formal and informal) between the different elements. In the final phase, a general discussion was conducted, collecting the outcomes of the previous discussions among the participants. These outcomes, representing the next steps towards implementing an OHRAS based on the existing system, were then prioritized.

All participants agreed on the importance of this meetings gathering people from different sectors to generate cross-sectoral perspectives, and to develop friendly and informal relationships. Also, systems-mapping and discussions on the One Health existing infrastructures and operations are very useful, allowing the identification of gaps, as well as strong points. Main conclusions included the need to establish a national community of practice in One Health, the reinforcement of communication and data sharing among sectors, and the reinforcement of One Health culture and awareness.

Stakeholders map Belgium

Example of a stakeholders analysis. This is the analysis done in Belgium and used to invite stakeholders to the systems mapping workshop with the focus on AMR. Important to realise that when another group of people would perform the analysis there will be differences.